
TECHNICAL MODERNITY, ECOLOGICAL DIMENSION AND CYBER SELF-REGULATION

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And a small economy can be big if it has an innovative product and a competitive offering. The decisive factor in developing the activities that led to the formation of the cybernetic concept was war [1]. The value system cannot be improved if we do not change its matrix. We define new assumptions. The emphasis is on increasing the dynamics of the system by increasing its flexibility but also by innovative creations. Has the interdisciplinary approach of science affected the development of the knowledge-based economy? It is always a question of the whole. We have the onset of strong semantic barriers between professions. It is a question of upgrading the interdisciplinary scientific method of stochastic systems management. The world of technologies and machines is in constant exponential growth, from the moment of birth of the first thought in a human being, through the current period, and further into the future, we are followed by the world of technology - machines [2]. Cybernetics is on duty to hold hands and technology and ecology. If the historical cybernetic scheme of instances in the relation between technology and ecology had been respected, we would not have mentioned ecology today. Evolutionarily and substantively, and functionally and developmentally, that relationship would be respected in accordance with nature.

Keywords: cybernetics, technical modernity, ecology, society, economy.

1. Introduction

Fast, faster, even faster. The acceleration velocity flows, the first derivative of the velocity vector, followed by the acceleration of the speed acceleration and the speed acceleration of the acceleration velocity. We are expecting a quantum computer and a bio chip. Knowledge of the cosmos, its origin and future, will open many horizons and introduce us to the world of new reality and imagination.

In the study of development, we have a time of disaggregation. The "single root cause" approach to the problem of underdevelopment has disappeared with the decline of the school of dependance, just as the unilinear approach has disappeared with the decline of the modernization paradigm. As a rule, illusions about development are destroyed by crises, and crises appear as errors in the assumed developmental continuity, which leads to the determination that there is no state of "development" but only continuous processes of change accepted as "development" or "underdevelopment", depending on the views of the individual.

2. Development of science and acceleration of changes

Science grows according to the law of exponential growth. Science grows similarly to a population. The population grows in proportion to the last generation. Science grows in proportion to the mass of knowledge left to us by the previous generation. Between 93% and 95% of all scientists who have ever studied science live today. All the legacy of the past is grandiose. However,

the number of prominent scientists still agrees with the percentage of the total number of people who are engaged in science !?

The cybernetic relationship between the needs for science and the financial system is at odds, because the number of scientists grows more or less in proportion to the square of the number of prominent scientists. If we want to increase the number of prominent scientists by 5, then we must increase the total number of scientists by 25.

On the other hand, the funds increase according to the fourth root of the number of scientists. If we increase the number of scientists by 3 times, the funds should be increased by 71 times. The number of researchers doubles every 12 years, which means that in each such interval there will be as many researchers as there were in the entire previous period [3]. In the last 60 years, the number of researchers has increased 19 times, which corresponds to the exponential development with a doubling period of 12 years.

Modern digital achievements result in creations that transcend nature, which emerges as a key hypothesis about evolution in the present time. Technical progress, which has the characteristic of universal diffusion, does not bypass any of the areas of economic and social activities [4].

Artificial intelligence and recognition theories are the products of the evolutionary imagination of the creative mind and practice. Exponential growth of science,

as well as results and existence, is not possible indefinitely, since there are no real conditions for growth that turn into absurd proportions, and as such a scientific system would necessarily disintegrate. Exponential growth does not stop all at once, but tries to grow exponential again with logistical behavior, along with the "braking" mechanism, when the conditions for that are created [5].

The scientific system produces a huge amount of parallel, as well as innovative information through fundamental, applied and developmental researches. Each of their applications or activities in any way causes changes of a certain content and intensity. The need to react, to head towards a change is the result of cyber actions, because the survival and duration of the organizational system assumes the existence of dynamic balance. The parameters of growth from nature are not so evident, they show a certain degree of limitation. After the fullness point, the growth rate stagnates or decreases. The decline in the growth rate of science is followed by adaptability to the existing environment. The general principle could be expressed by the following stance: the increase in the results of scientific work is proportional to the increase in the number of researchers and inversely proportional to the general number of researchers. The concentration of resources in science is analog to the level of concentration in industry. Resources, personnel and capacities are the holy trinity of economic science. It is a response to "macroscopic, multimolecular formations within which an intensive exchange of information takes place, where the transfer of information from one stable system to another in the process of evolution is characteristic." [6].

The basis of cybernetics is the mathematical theory of information. By applying objective research methods in both living and non-living systems, cybernetics cooperates in the mathematical generalization of a number of biological laws. Thanks to this, wide horizons and perspectives of new achievements have opened up before biology. Karl Marx points out that "science only reaches perfection when it succeeds in using mathematics." The message is that by using cybernetic concepts, especially information theory, we contribute to the further improvement of biological and analog natural, social and technical sciences.

Information exists and functions within the system and is determined by the organizational structure of the system itself. "The very structure of the system contains certain information. Common to all cybernetic systems is the presence of controlling and controlled parts, which are connected by communication channels through which various information circulates." [7].

It is necessary that every organizational system has a data strategy, because contemporary system of production, analysis, distribution and storage of data differs from the pre-digital era. The "Big Data" revolution has taken place. There has been an outbreak of a new type of unstructured data; information that is recorded but cannot be easily classified into orderly forms. Social networks are the biggest source of unstructured data. This data is generated in real time and continuously enable the business to analyze changes in feel-

ings, behaviors and conversations in details. The biggest source of unstructured data that quickly conquers us are sensors that find their position in everything around us and on our way to the world of ever-present networks [8].

3. Ecological dimension and cyber interaction

The inscription at the entrance to Stellenbosch University in South Africa reads: "Destroying of any nation does not require atomic bombs or intercontinental ballistic missiles. It just has to decrease the quality of education and students to pass examination by fraud. As a consequence: patients will die in the hands of such kind of doctors; buildings will fall, built by such kind of engineers; money is vanishing in the hands of such kind of economists; justice is evaporating in the hands of such kind of judges. The crash of education it is the crash of nation.

Why did we take this quote from the internet message? Unfortunately, the interaction between the educational and socio-economic system is preserved by its duration and not by suspension, it brings the system and its structure into a regressive state. Flexibility in decay is much faster and more efficient than the need for it in the development of organizational systems. A compromised education system produces cyber imbalances in the long run. The educational system of values as a subsystem of a great social system in interaction with it deepens the imbalance through the system of connections and their actions. There is a networking of negative action that causes a chain reaction. The emergence of any unknown cognitive information is beyond the ability of management systems to respond to "holes" in education. There is an increase in entropy, which is in line with the increase in the amount of misinformation perceived as information.

Current and future goals of sustainable development are in line with the concepts of educational - cultural and environmental activities. The issue of implementation and control is always debatable. The schedule of activities until 2030 sets 17 goals of sustainable development, in mutual interaction that promote the general call for activities aimed at reducing poverty, protecting the planet, the environment for prosperity. It is about economic inequalities, climate change, innovation ... The question is: How to plan and implement certain activities without disturbing the natural balance? A partnership between the state, the private sector, science and citizens is essential. Processes of reporting and control of business activities are necessary, especially for development areas where there is development continuity. Environmental adaptation processes should be part of the projected tasks. Management processes take place according to certain laws, which implies the existence of its own algorithm for a given system. The construction of algorithms requires theoretical communication of scientific disciplines such as: biochemistry, biophysics, ecology, technical sciences, mathematics and mathematical methods. Thanks to the interdisciplinarity that is the basis of the functioning of cybernetics, it is possible nowadays to solve every task and problem if its solution algorithm is known.

Inflation of diplomas that are worth nothing even though they are paid, putting them on the same level

with diplomas of quality universities, leads to the devaluation of acquired knowledge and the affirmation of ignorance. Dositej brought education and potatoes to Serbia. Potatoes are accepted!? Attacks on the education system is a project of Western "friends". Before World War II, the French issued diplomas for the Balkans. They were recognized only there, but not in France and its colonies. Even today, in two hours and for around 300 euros, one can get a "valid" doctoral degree from some prestigious European universities. The rating of high schools and the attitude "as many students as chairs" would be the beginning of the recovery of the biggest social polluter. The same goes for the health system? You can open a health institution if you meet the prescribed standards and most importantly, if you have an insurance contract and the algorithm says: all residents are insured. More than half of private health organizations do not know what a fiscal bill is! And only differences in prices! Why do we mention this, because there is a negative cyber interaction, just like for the education system because we have disorganization? The entropy of the system does not suffer empty. The hole in knowledge is filled with ignorance, and bridging the problem is done with mythological constructions of subjects, because the objective reality of illiterate sectarians is unknown.

.Feedback with linear dependence is most often used in engineering due to the ease of application of the system of linear differential equations. Nonlinear dependencies present a complex cybernetic problem due to the modeling of appropriate relationships between commands and results. In biological systems, nonlinearity of feedback provides the greatest adjustment at the expense of response extrapolation. Nonlinearity of feedback and the "exercise effect" are measures that have evolved to prevent fluctuations in systems in order to increase their accuracy.

Feedback is of the utmost importance in cybernetics. Feedback ensures the integrity, orderliness and purposefulness of the system. N. Wiener presents feedback as "a property that allows future behavior to be regulated on the basis of executive orders"[9]. Management and regulation of "ordinary" systems are based on homeostasis, monitoring and execution of certain programs and they are elements of complex cybernetic systems whose basic property is the ability of self-improvement through self-learning that dictates goal-orientation through purposefulness. The result is an increase in the level of organization of the system, an increase in information and decrease in entropy. "During the realization of the optimal control system, the task is set: to choose the structure and parameters of the control system so that in reality the processes of its movement take place in an optimal way [10]. Control actions should be created during the movement of the system.

4. Environmental Engineering and Newton's Laws

We are witnesses that of the 250 largest companies in the world, almost 95% report on the goals of environmental protection and sustainable development in their activities. These are economic and social goals.

In the real world, all human activities are governed by the laws of nature. Man is a biological entity with

reflective consciousness. There are actions that are not the result of human action. For instance, geomorphology, seasonal changes in solar radiation, climate, soil, water and soil distribution. Act and action in this area frame one-dimensional time and three-dimensional space as objectively given factors [11].

Changes are a condition for the development of organizational systems. We will identify some of the challengers, such as innovative technical and technological breakthroughs of the expected positive result, but there are also challengers of crisis potential both in the company and in the environment to which the company as a system reacts cybernetically. We emphasize the importance of management technology, as the oldest of all (mechanical, energy, information, digital) and which is the key to everything, including business success. The quality of management, not ownership, predominantly promotes the result of the company.

In the Spanish-speaking world, environmental engineering is defined as: "design, implementation and management of processes, products and services for prevention, limitation or restoration of the environmental damage in order to ensure sustainable development"[12].

In Anglo-Saxon countries, ecological engineering is considered to be: "the planning, designing and implementation of projects that combine natural resources in function of biodiversity and human society"[13].

In France, environmental engineering is defined as "the management of projects that apply the principles of environmental engineering in their implementation and supervision, and increase the immunity of the ecostructure." From the science point of view, "environmental engineering is seen as a unified activity of scientific results, techniques and practices through respect for environmental standards in resource management, design and construction of infrastructure, facilities and equipment in order to protect certain space, water and air"[14].

Ecological engineering promotes significant socio-economic advantages: better performance, lower material and energy costs, better output quality, cooperation between the environment and regulators, multiple dispersion of positive environmental impacts, and even the impact on the culture of work and behavior. Natural energy sources and self-regulating processes reduce operating and maintenance costs. Evolutionary actions in the present always refer to the framework order of economic structure and behavior, and unfortunately it cannot be predicted that the naivety of possible management teams regarding issues of order policy makes them miss enough understanding for the basis of their business.

The theory of evolution, modernly observed, is a process of real treatment of development flows, but also mistakes in the effort to establish the laws of evolution, the knowledge of which would allow us to predict future development trends. The theory of evolution is primarily an examination of the mechanism of evolution, those principles of action that have produced those forms of life that amaze us every hour and that are so purposefully adapted to their environment [15]. Adaptation abilities are not of the same importance in

all historical periods and do not take place at the same pace and with the same intensity. The same is true for disruptive factors that disrupt cyber stability through influences on parts of the network structure that construct integrity based on interoperability and allow the system to function as a whole. In times of stable social-economic states, the accent may be put on other factors, which can lead to one-sided specialization in the service of economic efficiency, which then can prove to be existentially threatening as soon as the assumptions that led to a certain situation, which may represent regression, stability or prosperity, disappear. Only then it is evident that ability to adjust is the most important features of organizational systems. Insolvency cases in recent years illustrate this in a worrying way [16].

Evolutionary management is a system-oriented series of enterprising activities, logical and understandable for the development of the company [17]. At the moment when the one-sided economic perspective of the company as a system were abandoned, we would have to establish the areas in which the orderliness of the system will seek support. The question is: how can it be changed and further developed? Understanding the enterprise as a system and its evolutionary character, its functioning determines the connections and effects of one system on another, lower but also higher levels of coverage, which shows that complex models of order that every real company shows, can never rest as a whole only on conscious planning, shaping and guiding, but that these are largely based on autonomous principles of the system's own dynamics, which, if we understand it, we can use, but which we can completely destroy with unreasonable intervention. In the developmental processes of socio-economic systems, gradualness and patience are special characteristics, similar to biological structure. Everything has its beginning, duration and variability, and the cybernetic laws of development and balance work, regardless of our knowledge of them. Knowledge of the behavior of biological systems is necessary for the development of socio-economic systems and their functioning. Then we are in mutually conditioned cybernetics. Analogy in modern computer machines and automatic control systems are built characteristics of cerebrum [18].

There is always resistance to changes, whether it is corrective to the existing or innovative as modernization. Help for adequate response can be found in the modification of Newton's laws to economic, cultural and social changes in general. Small language modifications are necessary in order to realize the thought process of adapting to the phenomenon of change in organizations.

First Law: the behavior of an organization will not change unless it is affected by an external force. If the success of the company is observed through the value of the placement of the output in a function of time, then the characteristics and quality of the output are not good. The reasons for their acceptance, but also active feedback, are in the environment. Under the influence of the main categories of actual and potential customers, the company's internal reaction to external challenges is triggered.

Second Law: the amount of behavior change will be directly proportional to the amount of effort put into it. "Amount of effort" raises the question of the effectiveness of different types of effort, and while it is clear that a major change in strategy requires major changes in sources of commitment, this process is not automatically accompanied by required changes in behavior.

Third Law: the resistance of an organization to change will be of the same value but in the opposite direction from the amount of effort invested in its change. As M. Davidson says in his book "The Transformation of Management"[19] this law keeps the performer of changes awake even at night. The more homogeneous, historically successful and natural the organization is in its composition, the less "sleep" the performer of changes can expect. The stronger the culture, the stronger the thrust. If no way can be found to channel external resistance, the result is a stalemate. If the performers of change are few and represent the only expression of external strength (1st Law), their chances of making significant decisions are small.

5. Technical modernity and ecological processes

"There are small things without which there are no big ones. There are small things that need to be talked about as big ones. Countless little things form the foundation of a great building of beauty, truth and goodness. There is nothing in the sky or in the air, everything is on earth. The spirit is a dragon, it flies high in the air, but the rope should be held firmly in the hands"[20], said the young Milan Kašanin. That rope is the stern, steering wheel, paddle, sail, standard, regulation, enter, law, rules and procedures, decisions. Every thing contains information as a logical means of thinking management. Deciding means managing. Own development, on one's own resources, preferably with a comparative advantage, is the best protection against negative action sensors coming from the international environment. There is nothing as sensitive as capital. Laws that differ in intensity and structure, but not in their nature, have affected the affirmation of cybernetics. The barrier between real (exact) and verbal (social) sciences has been broken. The functions of the system dominate, namely information management with autoregulatory characteristics of the system.

As far as ecology is concerned, the Affirmation and Meaningless Strategy is on the scene. With reindustrialization, where it is possible, it is necessary to realize the processes of affirmation and mastery of dominant techniques and technologies on a global scale, including environmental characteristics, in order not to devalue them before the period in which it is possible to reproduce things and money capital. Ecological reindustrialization through digitalization seems feasible, but it is necessary to enable companies and management teams and individuals to "hand over" innovations and technical, technological and IT innovations. By affirming intellectual capital, nurturing historical heritage and tradition, and the totality of available resources through a horizontal hierarchy (mobility of scientists and the capable for the benefit of the work done), it is possible to overcome the achieved and achieve the desired state of any subsystem and system as a whole.

Education is the biggest polluter and ignorance confirms that.

As a measure of technical modernity of means of work, we use in practice statistical categorization performed on the basis of the degree of mechanization or automation of the work process. In his book, Kvasha, a Soviet statistician, proposes a model for calculating the annual weighted average category of degrees of mechanization and automation, based on the installed power of electric motors. James Bright of Harvard presented a system with 17 degrees of mechanization and automation [21]. It starts from the way of regulation of means of work and affirms three criteria: manual, machine and self-regulation, and according to the energy source, two criteria: manual and machine. It is about the development contribution and methodological approach to automation, because under the influence of technical progress and radical innovative breakthroughs, there are moments and new criteria that are unknown to us today and which we cannot manage. Everything that can be described can be planned, so it can be managed.

The capacity profile and the production profile, through feedback, regulate the level of mechanization and automation of the work process. The capacity profile serves as a basis for deciding on the breadth of technological integration of production, defining investment needs and the breadth of forms of production and business cooperation (specialization, cooperation, typification), while the production profile defines production orientation and breadth of specialization and diversification of production. The expansion of the capacity profile is also reflected in the expansion of the domain of not only material production, but it is also actively involved in the processes of scientific research and development activities [22]. Historically, manual, mechanized and automated control of work processes follows the development trend of the evolutionary type. The ideogram shows that the number of operations of a managerial nature is qualitatively increasing along with the level of increasing the modernity of technological equipment. Integrating and aggregating equipment follows this trend. When profiling the production orientation and capacity of the company, we strive to create objective conditions for the rational application of technology with the highest degree of efficiency.

Integration and aggregation of basic processing techniques with the technique of transport-regulation-measurement-control-performance regulation-remote control and information-and cybernetic self-regulation at every achieved level of technical modernity of any system. Industry 4.0 happened to us. The evolutionary economy of a circular character and digital Darwinism cause many changes and solve them by the level of their achievements. On the ideogram we have shown a gradual - evolutionary process of integration and aggregation of basic processing techniques of different degrees of complexity with different levels of regulation techniques - transport - measurement - control - registration of effects - remote control and information - self - regulation. Health and ecology are in the first and second place on the matrix of values of a society, so it means that all issues related to ecology cannot be banned when asking them [23]. Due to the fact that they have become

dominant and manifested possibilities, digital technologies, which essentially enable the existence of the Internet, appear as the main driver of the modern economy and relations in society.

Digitization affirms the networked economy and develops communicative interaction on the principle of everyone with everyone and all with all. On the other hand, digitalization leads to drop in communication costs, systems are networked and therefore can interact individually and with everyone, which is another contribution to increasing levels of efficiency, planning success and continuous monitoring over time. The evolution of the work world takes place under the influence of technical progress and competition. However, there is no absolute progress without relative regress.

Modern technology is the main lever for solving environmental problems. The goal is to integrate environmental protection in advance at all stages of the production cycle - from production to waste disposal.

At the level of achievements of registered patents for environmental protection, 23% come from Germany, followed by the USA with 15% and Japan with 10%. Here are some examples where it is possible to effectively apply the achievements of innovative technologies for environmental protection. Carbon gas for heating, wind energy, coal electricity production in combined power plants with integrated coal gasification, gas and steam turbine power plant, ground heat, solar thermal energy, solar power plants or solar thermal power plants, solar plants as a type of power plant, energy from deposited gas, produced from garbage dumps, new production process in a steel power plant, holographic - optical light control, antique remediation technology. Constructed buildings with energy savings consider wood as the best building material.

It is renewable and an ecological resource. A small amount of energy costs is represented in the processing, unlike the production of other construction materials. At the same time, thermal insulation is ideal in the appropriate construction method. Research in the field of "double houses" made of wood, limestone, light bricks and concrete gave the following results: A wooden house made of pre-built building elements jumped with 46 kWh of energy for heating per m² per year. The German average of conventional construction houses, on the other hand, is 140 and 200 kWh. The new German regulation of heat protection allows a maximum of 85 kWh for new buildings, almost twice the value achieved in a wooden house.

Conclusions

Are we threatened by technical and technological catastrophes!? Wrong decisions from the past produce trouble in the present, because if the decisions had been good, we would not have had trouble. The price of economic growth is a consequence of the dynamics of technological development in which technical installations and capacities led by management technology and growing scientific knowledge are the basic determinants. If humanity continues to modernize in order to grow the economy, there is a danger of developing self-destructive potentials unless social structure and science are not adequately transformed and "reflective sci-

entific development" is not implemented as part of "reflective modernization". More and more dangers are being built into socio-economic dynamism. We design societies and risk areas [24]. However, this is not a human answer to human questions. Man's greatness consists in liberation from destiny, because he can oppose to everything around him only by himself, how successfully it depends on his knowledge as acting negentropy and there is a riddle of solving incoming and created problems.

In his book, Wiener "found a low degree of homeostasis of a developed class society, which he summarizes through the aspect of greater concentration of communication media, taken in the broadest sense, in the hands of a small class of rich people." The media, thus, serve the growing accumulation of power and wealth within a narrow social stratum, which Wiener defines as a basic "antihomoeostatic" element of society, or rather as a major factor in its structural instability. Cybernetics, therefore, cannot serve as a panacea, a magic cure, for the transformation of social structures and the healing of social evils"[23]. But it can pave the way for the people of knowledge to develop. It is not possible, at least for the time being, to prevent human curiosity and creativity in any way. What will happen to us are miraculous, complex, similar in action and on the principles of human functioning, as a system of higher order, shaped products of effective technology, machines, organizations.

With the development of specialization, which necessarily presupposes cooperation, it is possible to raise the level of technology, which means more equal participation and more equal cooperation in international economic relations and in the process of protection and affirmation of domestic production. Development of process technology capacity with a dominant level of technical modernity, especially those based on reproductive raw materials of agricultural origin, where the process of devaluation and competitive duration is longer, it is possible to start a new selection of investments as the largest form of savings and, depending on capital flow, to ensure its dispersion onto other sectors of social economy. The new macroeconomy is focused on the economy of supply and retires both neoliberalism and Keynesianism. That is why a reaction is needed before the fact and that is why new people are needed. Humanity is an extension of natural creativity, with humanity creating what nature cannot. Man-made systems of organizational nature are artificial systems, but in many ways, they correspond to nature in the processes of their functioning, and not only in the field of resources. Modern complex digital technology produces creations that go beyond the natural. It is a key hypothesis about evolution in the present time, it is a fact that we identify on the basis of the theory of recognition and artificial intelligence as the result of the evolutionary imagination of the creative mind and practice.

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